

“*ROGAMADAU PARIKSHETA*” WSR to Survey Study on Sandhigata Vata

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Abstract:- Sandhigata Vata is one among the 80 Nanatmaja Vata Vikaras. Sandhigata Vata . Osteoarthritis is the most common joint disease among human beings today and introduced as synonym to Sandhivata. Osteoarthritis rate in India is around 22% to 39%. Sandhigata Vata mainly occur due to faulty life style of people. In this study, a total of 172 patients were registered, two types of study was done in this survey. In first type study was done on basis of symptoms experienced by peoples and in second type study was done on basis of faulty life style of people. All the symptoms of Sandhigata Vata and life style of people were given a score, depending upon their severity.

Keywords:- Sandhigata Vata, Osteoarthritis, Vata Vyadhi.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sandhigata Vata is one of the most prevalent joint disorders of present era. Basically it is a degenerative disorder usually associated with ageing.^[1] In Vriddhavastha there is predominance of Vata Dosha.^[2] So, old persons are susceptible to various types of Vatavyadhi. One such disorder is Sandhigata Vata. As per Acharya Caraka, it is manifested by Shotha (swelling of the joint), Vatapurnadriti Sparsha (on palpation, appears as if joint is a leather bag inflated with air) and Prasarana Akunchanayoh Pravrittishcha Savedana (pain

while making efforts for extension and flexion of the joint).^[3] As per Acharya Madhavakara, when aggravated Vata is localized in Sandhi (joint), it destroys the joint and produces Shula (pain in the joint) and Atopa (abnormal sound due to damage of joint or crepitus).^[4]

Sandhigata Vata can be correlated with Osteoarthritis of knee joint due to similarity in clinical features. Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common type of arthritis. It occurs with a variety of patterns in synovial joints and is characterized by cartilage loss with an accompanying peri articular bone response. It is probably not a single disease entity but a multifactorial process in which mechanical factors have a central role. The whole joint structure including cartilage, ligaments, synovium and capsule are involved. Pathologically, there are significant inflammation of articular and periarticular structures and alteration in cartilage structure.^[5]

➤ Aims and Objectives:

- To study which symptoms are mostly seen is sandhigat vata patients.
- To study due to which life style patients are getting sandhigat vata.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Literary data was collected from Samhitas.
- Articles related to topic were studied.
- A questionnaire consisting of 17 questions regarding symptoms of Sandhigata Vata and life style which results to form Sandhigata Vata.
- The received data was collected, studied and compiled.

➤ *Type of Study:*

Survey through goggle form which was circulated through social media.

➤ *Survey:*

A total of 172 responses were collected among age groups 20 to 60. Occupations included students, teachers, doctors, homemakers, architects, Farmers, engineers, designers, educators, developers, businessmen, etc. The questions related to symptoms of sandhigat vata and question related to their life style were asked and data was collected.

Table 1 for Pain:

<p>Which kind of pain you experience? 80% responded for pulling type of pain and 20% responded for pricking type of pain.</p>	
<p>When you experience pain? 25% responded for pain present whole day, 8% responded for pain present only in morning, 26% responded for pain present only at night and 41% responded for pain present after walking</p>	

Table 2 For Swelling:

<p>Can you hear any kind of sound from the joint while walking or during work? 71% responded for Yes, 29% respondent for No.</p>		
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Table 3 for Life Style:

<p>● What you eat more? 67% responded for vegetarian, 33% responded for non-vegetarian.</p>		
<p>● Do you get proper sleep? 83% responded for Yes, 17% responded for No.</p>		

III. DISCUSSION

In the present study, lifestyle of people and symptoms of Sandhigata vata are observed on the basis of questions regarding symptoms and lifestyle of people.

According to symptoms, 63% patients have joint pain. Among them among them most hello pulling type of pain then pricking type of pain. Most of the patient experience pain after walking and pain present whole day. Knee joint And lower back is mainly affected. Most of the patients does not have swelling in the joints only 12% peoples have swelling in the joint in that knee joint is mostly affected. Most of the patients (71%) are having sound from the joint while walking or during work. in the symptoms, most of the Symptoms are of Sandhigat vata.

According to lifestyle of the people, Most of the people have proper sleep time. Only few that is 9% peoples have non-proper sleep time, that is between 12 AM to 2 AM. 14% people does not get proper sleep. Most of the people work in AC (81%). Most of the people eat vegetarian food, only 33% eat non-vegetarian food. 13% people eat food because it in meal time but not hungry and 11% eat little quantity of food multiple times and 40% people sleep in day time.

So, according to the data, we can say, that most of the people suffers from Sandhigata vata due their faulty life style .

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